

Biomedical Named Entity Recognition for Substance Abuse: Using BERT-CRF and Large Language Models for Spanish Clinical Data

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Abstract

Automated extraction of substance abuse patterns from clinical narratives is critical for public health surveillance but remains challenging for non-English languages due to limited annotated resources. The IX BioCreative Challenge, "Large Language Models for Clinical and Biomedical NLP," included a task focused on the detection and characterization of substance use and abuse in clinical texts. Participants were provided with an annotated corpus of 1,500 Spanish clinical notes, labeled for substance-related entities (ToxNER subtask) and their associated attributes (ToxUse subtask). This study evaluates two approaches for named entity recognition: (1) a supervised BERT-CRF pipeline, combining a fine-tuned Spanish biomedical transformer with conditional random fields, enhanced by Optuna hyperparameter optimization and rule-based data augmentation to address class imbalance, and (2) a zero-shot method using the DeepSeek [1] LLM API with direct prompting. Evaluation on the challenge's blinded test set revealed F1-scores of 0.71 (ToxNER) and 0.53 (ToxUse) for the BERT-CRF model, compared to 0.44 and 0.31, respectively, for the DeepSeek API.

Keywords

Named Entity Recognition, Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers, Conditional Random Fields, Large Language Models

1. Introduction

Substance abuse disorders represent a growing global health burden [2]. The Office on Drugs and Crime reports an annual increase in drug-related crimes in many countries around the world, indicating that the problem of uncontrolled substance use is worsening [3].

Early identification through clinical documentation could prevent deaths from overdose and substance-related complications such as drug-drug interactions, postoperative complications, and others. However, current natural language processing tools fail to adequately analyze non-English medical records, creating surveillance gaps.

The BioCreative IX Challenge [4] addressed this pressing need through the ToxHabits task [5]. This initiative provided 1,500 annotated Spanish clinical notes, creating a standardized benchmark for substance use and abuse detection along with the named entities that characterize them. Our study uses this resource to train a model based on a combination of artificial neural networks (Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers, BERT) and conditional random fields (CRF) [6] to extract instances of use and abuse of various substances (ToxNER subtask) and recognize the names of entities that characterize them. Furthermore, we are conducting research on the possibility of using large language models (DeepSeek[1]) for these tasks that are not specialized for the field of biology and medicine to extract relevant information.

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2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Brief description of the ToxHabits subtasks and the corpus

Track 3 of the BioCreative IX challenge suggests that participants solve two subtasks [5][7]. In the first of these, ToxNER, participants must recognize the names of substances whose abuse is described in the texts of clinical notes in Spanish. These substances are divided into four types: alcohol, cannabis, tobacco, and drugs; otherwise, in the corpus annotation, they are also called "triggers". In the second task, ToxUse, it is necessary to recognize the names of so-called arguments: terms that characterize abuse. These arguments are also divided into several types: Type, Method, Amount, Frequency, Duration and History[8]. The "Type" argument characterizes the specific substance which abuse was documented. The "Method" argument characterizes the way in which a substance was abused (for example, intravenously). The "Amount" argument refers to the amount of substance abused. The "Frequency" argument describes the periodicity of substance use (for example, each day). The "Duration" argument indicates the time that has passed from the first use of the substance to the moment the clinical record is formed or use ceases. The "History" argument includes periods of time when substance use was stopped.

The corpus is presented as a set of files: text, with the texts of clinical notes, and json, annotations to them. The corpus is divided into two parts: training (1,174 texts) and test (300 texts). Initially, participants were offered only a training dataset to form the architecture and preliminary assessment of the architecture of the models. Then they were provided with a test dataset, but without annotations to the clinical notes.

2.2. Named entity recognition within the framework of the ToxNER and ToxUse subtasks using the BERT-CRF model

The proposed system builds upon a multi-stage neural architecture based on a pre-trained BERT [9] model (bert-base-spanish-wwm-cased[10]) that has been enhanced with several specialized components to address the unique challenges of biomedical text mining in Spanish. The architecture strategically combines the contextual understanding capabilities of transformers with the sequence modeling strengths of conditional random fields.

2.2.1. Description of the model structure

The foundation of the system utilizes BETO (Spanish BERT-based trained with whole-word masking), which provides contextualized word representations. The model processes input texts segmented into tokens, with a maximum sequence length of 512 tokens to accommodate typical clinical documentation. Unlike standard implementations, we incorporate dynamic gradient check-pointing during training, which reduces GPU memory requirements while maintaining computational throughput.

Building on the base BERT[9] model, the system incorporates an auxiliary attention mechanism that operates on the transformer outputs. This additional transformer encoder layer employs eight attention heads and a 3072-dimensional feedforward network, specifically designed to capture long-range dependencies in clinical documentation. The inclusion of relative position embeddings helps model the syntactic patterns characteristic of medical texts, where temporal expressions and diagnostic criteria often appear distant from their associated trigger or argument mentions.

The architecture ends with a CRF decoding layer that models sequential dependencies between entity tags. This component learns transition constraints that explicitly encode valid IOB tag sequences[11], preventing biologically implausible predictions such as an "I-DURATION" tag following a "B-SUBSTANCE" tag (for the ToxUse subtask).

2.2.2. Data preprocessing

The data processing pipeline begins with careful alignment and conversion to the IOB format, where *B* is used to mark the first token of the named entity, *I* is used to mark all other tokens of named entities

except the first one, and *O* is used to mark tokens that do not belong to named entities. A specialized text augmentation component addresses data scarcity through controlled transformations that preserve label integrity. The augmenter employs synonym replacement using a curated medical lexicon, along with context-preserving word deletion and swapping operations.

2.2.3. Model training

The model training process incorporated hyperparameter optimization using Optuna's Bayesian framework. This approach automatically identified the optimal training configurations through the search strategy. The optimization targeted key hyperparameters that govern model performance and training dynamics.

A Tree-structured Parzen Estimator sampler guided the search process through the hyperparameter space. This method explored combinations of hyperparameters while focusing on promising regions. The optimization evaluated fifteen distinct configurations to balance exploration and computational efficiency.

The search space included critical training parameters. Learning rates varied logarithmically between $1e-6$ and $5e-5$ to properly scale gradient updates. Batch sizes tested values of 4, 8 and 16 to find the optimal balance between memory usage and gradient estimation quality. The optimizer configuration included epsilon values ranging from $1e-8$ to $1e-6$ for numerical stability.

Dropout rates between 0.1 and 0.5 were evaluated for both attention and hidden layers. Layer normalization epsilon values were tuned from $1e-6$ to $1e-5$ to maintain stable activations.

Training efficiency optimizations were also included. The system tested gradient accumulation steps from 1 to 4 to enable batch processing. Warm-up ratios between 0 and 0.3 helped stabilize early training. A successive halving pruner automatically terminated underperforming trials to conserve computational resources.

Performance assessment was independently performed on the training set using the list of hyperparameters obtained for the best model: 80 percent of the data set was used for training and 20 percent for validation. The IOB labels obtained during the prediction were compared with the IOB labels provided in the annotation. Based on the detection of true positive, false positive, and false negative prediction results, the metrics precision, recall, and F1-score were calculated.

The hyperparameter optimization, training of the model and evaluation of its performance on the internal training sample were carried out using graphics video memory (RTX 4070, 12 GB).

2.3. Named entity recognition within the framework of the ToxNER and ToxUse subtasks using DeepSeek API

To explore the capabilities of large language models trained on large amounts of data (not just biomedical), we tried using automated queries to DeepSeek using Python. For each of the subtasks, a prompt was generated that set the role of DeepSeek as a specialist in biology and medicine whose task is to find named entities associated with the use of various substances in a clinical text in Spanish. The difference in the prompts was only in the entity types difference in the two subtasks; at the same time, detailed but capacious descriptions were provided for each of the DeepSeek types. The prompt also set a structured output format: "named entity|start symbol position|end symbol position|named entity type".

It is noteworthy that when manually setting up the prompt, it was noted that the greatest difficulty for a large language model is determining the correct position of a named entity in the text. Therefore, having received the structured output generated by the large language model, we performed a procedure for refining the positions of named entities in the text by simply searching for a substring (name) in a string (text).

Table 1

Hyperparameters and F1-score of the best model obtained as a result of optimization

Parameters	ToxNER	ToxUse
F1-score (micro-average)	0.7876	0.6732
Learning rate	4.6469e-05	2.8347e-05
Batch size	8	8
Number of training epochs	5	10
Weight decay	0.0465	0.0872
Warm-up ratio	0.0169	0.1208
Gradient accumulation steps	2	4

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Named entity recognition based on BERT-CRF model

Training and selection of hyperparameters for each BERT model took no more than three hours, and obtaining predictions on the test sample took no more than 20 minutes, which may indicate the advantage of our model in terms of computational capacity. The data of the best models for subtasks obtained during the prediction on the training sample (20 percent of the total volume) are presented in the table 1.

The results of the model performance assessment on the test sample, which was conducted by the organizers, turned out to be lower: the F1-score in the ToxNER subtask was equal to 0.71 (precision 0.83, recall 0.65), and in the ToxUse subtask was equal to 0.53 (precision 0.47, recall 0.6). The difference in accuracy between the two subtasks appears to stem from the nature of the annotated terms. In the first subtask, the annotated terms are more specialized, which makes them stand out distinctly from the surrounding text. In contrast, the second subtask involves terms that may belong to everyday vocabulary, resulting in less noticeable differences compared to clinical texts. These texts mainly consist of descriptive patient history records, which further diminishes the contrast. It should be noted that, despite the identical architectures of the models used, there is a shift between the ratios of recall and precision: in the ToxNER subtask, the value of precision is greater than recall, while in the ToxUse subtask, the opposite is true – recall exceeds precision. This may be due to the different hyperparameters used in the models, as well as the different nature of the objects being recognized.

3.2. Named entity recognition using large language model

When using the DeepSeek API, the prediction performance was assessed only on the test sample since the behavior of LLMs can vary across different runs under the same conditions. Moreover, using the DeepSeek API eliminates the need for additional model fine-tuning, thereby removing the requirement for a dedicated training dataset – or even research based on it. The average processing time for one text of the test sample was 34 seconds, but this assessment may be biased due to the different network load and large language model by itself at different points in time. As for the costs in tokens, the double processing was performed using the set of texts from the test sample. In particular, we used the prompt for the ToxNER subtask and the ToxUse subtask separately. As a result, slightly more than 1.5 million tokens were generated.

The greatest difficulty for the model was the correct identification of the positions of named entities in the text - in almost 90 percents of cases, the large language model indicated positions that did not correspond to reality. The challenge organizers were sent the results with adjusted positions, but when assessing the predictive ability, low values were still obtained: the values of F1-score in the subtasks ToxNER and ToxUse were 0.44 (precision 0.57, recall 0.36) and 0.31 (precision 0.38, recall 0.26), respectively. A full comparison of the predictive efficiency of both algorithms presented in this work is impossible at this stage due to the lack of data on the results of the work of other teams.

3.3. Conclusion

Thus, the task of recognizing named entities in Spanish-language texts turned out to be a very challenging task using approaches common in the field of named entity recognition. It is worth noting that the authors' lack of knowledge of the Spanish language had a negative impact on the construction of the models. Moreover, using large language models for the task of recognizing named entities associated with the use of substances turned out to be inaccurate.

Since the challenge was launched recently and the corpus used in it has not yet seen widespread adoption, a precise comparison of model performance is currently unfeasible. However, existing literature describes algorithms for recognizing biological and chemical named entities in Spanish texts, independent of substance use or abuse contexts. For instance, R. A. A. Jonker [12] proposed a Conditional Random Fields (CRF)-based algorithm that achieves an F1-score of 0.93 for identifying chemical named entities. While the metrics reported in that study are higher, comparing our algorithm to the authors' approach primarily serves to outline directions for future improvement.

We hope that experience of our Orekhovihi team in building models for recognizing substance use-related named entities in Spanish-language clinical notes will be useful to the scientific community in further improving models for this task.

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